

Original Research Article

PRINCIPALS’ ADMINISTRATIVE STRATEGIES AND TEACHERS JOB PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN OBIO/AKPOR AND PORT HARCOURT LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS OF RIVERS STATE

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ABSTRACT: The study investigated principals’ administration strategies and teacher’s job performance in public senior secondary schools in Obio Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas in River State. The study adopted the correlational research design. This was suitable for determining the relationship that exists between dependent and independent variables under the study. The population of the study consist of all the 1,297 academic staff in the 21 Senior Public Secondary Schools in Obalga L.G.A and all the 708 academic staff in the 16 senior public secondary schools in Phalga L.G.A of Rivers State. The sample for the study was 700 teachers who arrived through a random sampling technique, representing 53% of the population in which 12 Schools were selected. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument was titled: “Principals’ Administrative Strategies and Teachers’ Job Performance Questionnaire” (PASTJPO). The items were responded to on a modified Likert scale of four points rating, thus, Strongly Agree (SA) =4 points, Agree (A) =3, Disagree (D) =2, Strongly Disagree (SD) =1. The weighted point was added as $4+3+2+1=10/4=2.5$, thus, 2.50 is the criterion mean. Therefore, the remark for any item below 2.5 was disagreed with and agreed for any item of 2.5 and above. The instrument for this study was subjected to face and content validation two experts in the field of measurement and evaluation. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability index value of .760. Data Analysis was done using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while Pearson product correlation was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that principals’ motivation, effective supervision and communication pattern strategies enhance teachers’ job performance in senior public secondary schools in Rivers State. The study concluded that principals’ administration strategies enhance teachers’ job performance in public senior secondary schools in Obio Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas in River State. It was recommended among others that the administration of various Secondary Schools should always as a matter of effectiveness, supervise their teachers to ensure they are quickened to deliver their service competently.

Keywords: Administration, Motivation, Principal, Strategies, Supervision

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INTRODUCTION

The success and development of the secondary school system depend on the quality and nature of the principal's administrative strategies. The principal is the coordinator of the entire secondary school activities and maintains a harmonious relationship with the teachers as subordinates to ensure the success of the school administration. Nwadani (2008) asserted that the principal is the fulcrum upon which the success or failure of school administration revolves around, noting that the principal must maintain close ties with his teachers in the achievement of school goals. The ultimate goal of education administration at all levels is to develop an all-inclusive and quality education that is accessible and relevant for self-reliance. This is guided by the understanding that good education contributes significantly to economic growth, improvement of employment prospects and income-generating opportunities for sustainable development.

Several administrative strategies exist to assist the principal in carrying out his day-to-day activities. An administrator who ignores these strategies is likely to encounter problems in the task of school administration. Hence, administration is seen as a collection of processes dealing with the various ways in which human and material resources are utilized to achieve set goals in an organization. These strategies include such elements as planning, effective leadership, effective supervision, principal's communication pattern, decision-making, organizing, coordinating motivating, directing, evaluating, staffing and budgeting. Enyi in Ogbonnaya (2013) stressed that the administrative process can therefore be regarded as the total of the various processes of planning, organizing, stimulating, coordinating, staffing, budgeting, communicating, and evaluating, which aid administrators in the utilization of resources in the achievement of organizational goals.

The administrative dealings of various secondary schools in Rivers State seem to have been hindered by numerous problems. These problems may include poor supervision, leadership styles of the principal, poor communication patterns, lack of motivation, lack of principal-teacher relationship, no proper monitoring of teachers' activities, inadequate facilities, inadequate funding, conflict among teachers and principals etc. Some principals in Rivers State seem to lack vision, there appear to be inadequate job analysis and work plan with poor instructional supervision which culminated in poor curriculum delivery in schools and consequently poor academic performance by the students.

School systems globally are faced with the challenge of how to advance teaching and learning outcomes which can be achievable through competent school monitoring (Ngovihi, 2016). Teachers need school monitoring to work harder no matter their level of experience and devotion. Without school monitoring, both teachers and principals regress fast in their job performance. The author further asserted the strength of any educational system and the value of the students, thus, instructional supervision is needed to improve the quality of the teachers who will in turn develop their profession.

The administration of public secondary schools in Nigeria and Obio Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas in Rivers State rests on the shoulders of the principal who is the leader, controller and custodian of both academic and extra-curricular activities of the school. The principal is the chief executive of the school, who provides instructional leadership by coordinating curricular, and co-curricular programmes and is also responsible for the general administration of secondary schools. As instructional leaders, principals' administrative tasks may include motivation supervision, monitoring, assessment, evaluation and dissemination of

current information on management and academic techniques to teachers, leading to effective teaching and learning processes. The principal may also be described as an executive head of the school (Achimugu, 2000) because of the way he makes decisions and implements its policies and programmes. Other words to describe a principal are “Boss”, “Leader”, “Head”, “Director”, “Adviser” and “Problem solver”.

Good teachers are skilled not only in instructional methods, but also in evaluation and assessment practices that allow them to gauge individual student’s needs, and this in reality is not too far from leadership effectiveness. For this study, the researcher will dwell on the following administrative strategies of principals namely: motivational strategy, supervision, and principal’s communication pattern strategies. Thus, a situation whereby principals fail to adopt effective administrative strategies in managing the schools might affect teacher’s commitment. Many of the teachers in such situations will not give their best performances while executing their primary duties and students who are always at the receiving end, suffer the consequences. The poor situation of many public secondary schools in Obio Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas, which are matters of school administration seems to make it impossible for quality teaching and learning to triumph. This situation which has created a lot of difficulties towards the realization of quality education, made the researcher embark on this study, to determine the administrative strategies employed by public secondary school principals in promoting teachers' job performance in Obio Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

The quality, effectiveness and efficiency of education services depend on the availability of skilled experienced and competent education professionals. It is the expectation of the government, parents and even the students that quality education is received by students in Nigeria public secondary schools through the adoption of appropriate administrative strategies by the principals. In Rivers State, there appear to be principal administrative deficiencies in public secondary schools that have led to poor teachers' job performance. They are manifested in a lack of commitment to the performance of their duties. Secondary schools were established for society as a means of producing quality students who can be self-reliant, and who can serve as good inputs to the tertiary education levels. It was expected that everybody within the secondary schools including the principals, teachers, non-teaching staff and even students, play active roles in modifying the behaviour of secondary school students through teaching, learning and guidance. Sadly, many public secondary school teachers in Obio /kpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas of Rivers State have been observed to be ineffective in their job performance and this is attributed to principals’ poor administrative functions.

Observations and some visits to some public secondary schools in the aforementioned Local Government Areas have shown that there seem to be poor principals' administrative strategies which have led to poor teacher job performance in secondary schools in the areas. This can be seen in the areas of ineffective leadership styles, poor instructional supervision, poor teaching and principal relationships, poor communication patterns and poor motivational strategies among others. The failure to use appropriate administrative strategies to enhance teachers' job performance by public secondary school principals, has led to poor academic achievement among public secondary school students in the Local Government Area, high drop-out rate and high rate of examination malpractice, poor reading and writing cultures among others. The above situation leads the researcher to investigate Principal’s Administrative

Strategies and Teacher's job performance in senior public secondary school in Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas in Rivers State.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

This study aims to investigate the relationship between principals' administrative strategies and teacher's job performance in senior public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor and Port Harcourt Local Government Areas in Rivers State. Specifically, the study objectives are to:

- Examine how the principal's motivational strategy enhances teachers job performance in senior public secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Analyze principal's effective supervision strategy in assessing teachers' note of lesson and teachers instructional delivery in senior public secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Examine the influence of principal's communication pattern strategy on teachers' job performance in senior public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

- How does principal's motivational strategy enhance teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State?
- How does principal's effective supervision strategy improve teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State?
- How does good principal's communication pattern strategy, enhances teachers job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested in the study at a 0.05 level of significance:

- There is no significant relationship between principals' motivational strategy and teacher's job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools Rivers State.
- There is no significant relationship between principals' effective supervision strategy and teacher's job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.
- There is no significant relationship between principals' communication pattern strategy and teacher's job performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATION

Principalship

The school principal is the most complex and contradictory figure in the pantheon of educational leadership. The principal is both the administrative director of educational policy and a building manager, both an advocate for school change and the protector of bureaucratic stability. Authorize to be employer, supervisor, professional figurehead, and inspirational leader. The

principals core training and identity is as a classroom teacher. Standing squarely between state institutions and the classroom, assigned both to promote large-scale initiative and to solve immediate day-to-day problems, the principal carries multiple and often contradictory responsibilities, wears many hats, and moves swiftly between multiple roles in the course of one day.

A single person, in a single professional role, acts on a daily basis as the connecting link between a large bureaucratic system and the individual daily experiences of a large numbers of children and adult. A principal is the head administrator of a school, especially a secondary school. Encyclopedia of education (2012) posited that the title principal is an appropriate designation for the chief administrator of a school. Principals are the executive head of secondary schools. The early school principalship was given to any teacher found to possess some sign of demonstrable administrative ability.

A teacher with academic qualification and the right type of personality could be appointed the administrative head in addition to full-time teaching duty. Many of such principals were preoccupied with such takes as scheduling, attendance taking, reporting among others. The idea of a principal serving as a teacher as well as an administrator continues today in small urban communities and most rural areas (Ukeje, 2010). As school became more complex, the principal was relieved at least some part of the teaching duties. In Nigeria schools, the principalship has evolved from the position and performance of teachers. Hence, the title principal usually refers to the head of a secondary school or post-primary institution (Aderounmu & Ehiamentalo 2005).

The principals of a school among other things is a public relations officer. He makes sure that all the staff are put to good use by apportioning work to them according to their qualification and ability. He is expected to know the community within which the school exists and to establish and maintain a cordial relationship between the school and the community. The principal is to take the initiative in translating the school to the community so that members of the community could take keen interest in the school and its activities by helping to back the laws made by the school authority. The school is for community and the people must be bought to participate in some of the activities of the school. Each school must have Parents Teachers Association (PTA) and the principal must work hard to keep it active. At this point both the parents, principal and teachers come together to look at the various problems facing classroom management.

The secondary school principal plays a vital role in relation to the community (Dada cited in Ameh, 2012). They are responsible for informing the public about the school, establishing confidence in the institution, and relying on community support to maintain the education program. Additionally, they should develop awareness of the importance of education in a democracy and improve partnerships by uniting parents and teachers to meet children's educational needs. The principal should also integrate the home, school, and community to improve educational opportunities, evaluate the school's offerings and the needs of the community's children, and correct any misunderstandings about the school's aims and objectives.

Principals play a crucial role in fostering positive relationships between schools and their surrounding communities (Obeogbulem, 2004 in Nnebedum, 2007). They should be accessible, courteous, and open to feedback, sharing both challenges and successes with the community. By doing so, they can build trust and promote a sense of collaboration, ultimately enhancing educational outcomes. Effective communication, active community engagement, and valuing non-teaching staff are also essential strategies for principals to foster positive school-community relations (Obeogbulem, 2004 in Nnebedum, 2007).

Administration

Administration is the cautious and precise plan in the utilization of resources (human and material), exploitation of circumstance and opportunities goals of a given organization. Within the educational sector, administration is the coordination of all school resources (human and material) by way of planning, sorting out, guiding and controlling events and activities in the school setting so as to accomplish set educational targets (Nwachukwu, 2008). The organizational approach used by administrator in achieving clearly defined goals is referred to as administrative behaviour. The dimensions of administrative behaviour include motivation, staff involvement in decision making, communication and development among other characteristics. (Ijaiya, 2016). The characteristics that form administrative behaviour to a significant extent determine the dynamics of employees within any organization. Appropriate administrative behaviour has the potential to raise the morale of staff and arouse them to perform maximally. Thus, the vitality of all educational organization, the willingness of school staff to contribute to the attainment of the goals of higher education is hinged on the administrative behaviour of school leaders.

For a school or department head to achieve administrative effectiveness, his policy and style of administration must reflect on personal attributes, ability to ensure individual member satisfaction and stringent procedure of attaining organizational goals (Madison et al., 2010). He/she is supposed to possess the ability to lead and control the effort of staff, encourage team work and co-operation among members, define tasks for the staff, organize and co-ordinate all the units towards common objectives. Ukeje (2009) considered administration as the extent to which organizations achieve their objectives within minimum expenditure of time and money by mobilizing human resources. This position has been corroborated by Egbo (2009), who saw administration as the formation and implementation of policies which help organizational leaders to do the right thing, Egbo further added that administration concerns the bringing together of resources that will eventually result in goal attainment.

According to Edmonds and Lezotte (2012), school administration is one which demonstrates the following criteria:

- A small or greater percent of all students at each grade level demonstrate minimum academic mastery and are prepared to succeed in the next grade anywhere.
- There shall be no significant difference in the proportion of students demonstrating academic mastery as a function of socio-economic class.

For this school of thought, administration or an effective school administration is that which combines external and internal variables, to ensure that it achieves the purpose of its existence in the society.

Teacher

The term teacher is used in this work to mean those who work in schools, providing education for pupils and students in educational institutions like secondary schools. Teachers are considered as the heart and soul of every education system. They are the key players who

transmit knowledge and enhance true learning in global education (Smith, 2000). Teachers are also referred to as all persons in school who are responsible for instruction of pupils or students in curriculum. It includes only the members of tutorial or academic staff. Teachers are placed in central focus because teachers, as professional workers and persons, are lenses through which much of the organized endeavour called education is brought to focus upon the end object of the endeavour.

In professional usage, a teacher is a person trained or recognized and (in some case) employed to help learning in a classroom situation so that the set education goals could be achieved. The global mindedness of teachers is often linked to the knowledge, attitude and skills development of students. These factors contribute in enhancing students capabilities to face the world challenges with confidence. Pitsoe (2013) observed that the quality of teachers has a direct impact on student learning. Therefore, their professional development is crucial to maintain the standard of education. Generally, a teacher is one who has undergone some training programmed and equipped with basic knowledge, drills and skills peculiarly for him to bring about changes and outcomes to an individual called learners. It can be deduced from the above definitions that teachers are those who have been exposed to a period of training, specifically designed to equip them with knowledge, rudiments, principles and practice of teaching.

In absence of the teachers, the school is something else and the students a kin to yam tendrils without stake and stakers. UNESCO (2017) said that the teacher is the spark that fits the whole development process, the key man in the drive to progress. Teachers are no doubt needed physically and in great quantity because of the individual roles they play in the educational system. The roles of teachers are many. The teacher is seen as a researcher, receiver of knowledge, disseminator of knowledge, a helper, facilitator, a guide etc.

Teacher Job Performance

Teaching is generally recognized as one of the most important and challenging occupations in contemporary society (Vesely et al., 2013). These professionals are regarded to be responsible for their students' academic achievement as well as social and emotional development (Elias & Arnold, 2006). Given the heavy demands and expectations in terms of students' development, teachers' job performance which is tied to students' outcomes. (Hwang et al., 2017), is of crucial concern for a variety of stakeholders, including principals, parents, policymakers, and society at large (Alrajhi et al., 2017). According to Casting (2016), job performance can be seen as execution, conduct, compliance or conformity with stated decisions or directives issued by a super-ordinate or demanded by a job. This shows that performance of any job must be according to the pattern set for performing such tasks. Ajilabi (2000) opined that teachers' job performance is a judicious devotion and dedication to the achievement of standards within and outside school setting.

Teachers' instructional tasks are statutory curricula functions that are performed by the teachers to enable learners achieve the set educational goals in schools. This m ultimately depends on the commitment of principals and teachers to make judicious and adequate use of both human and material resources to ensure quality assurance in the teaching-learning process. Teachers' quality is manifested in their knowledge of the subject matter, skills and competencies in the teaching and learning processes, which leads to the accomplishment of the stated educational goals. This means that the real teacher must possess the qualities for effective teaching and pleasant learning within the school setting. He must know what he is to teach, how

he is to teach, and whom he is to teach. This purpose is to deliver the curriculum efficiently, so as to achieve the set goals and standard in schools (Koleoso, 2012; Makinde & Alao, 2008).

Secondary School

Secondary school refers to the schooling offered after a primary school. Students spend six years in secondary school that is three years in JSS (Junior Secondary School) and three years of SSS (Senior Secondary School). The Senior Secondary School Examination (SSCE) is taken at the end of the SS3. The West African Examination Council (WAEC) administers both exams. Secondary schools are classified as private and public. Where the private schools are maintained by private individuals, groups and organization, public schools are restricted to those schools that are related to government schools. Secondary education is the formal education where children receive education after primary education and before the tertiary stage within the range of 12 and 18 years (FRN, 2014). It is aimed at preparing individuals for useful living in the society and higher education.

Secondary education is the education that normally takes place in secondary schools. It takes place after primary education and may be followed by higher education or vocational training. Secondary education often referred to as a high school; is a school which provides secondary education between the ages of 11 and 19 depending on location, after primary school and before higher education. Children usually go to secondary school between the ages of 11 and 16 years, and end between the ages of 16 and 18 years. In the content of this study, secondary school refers to the education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary stage.

Administrative Strategies

Administration is conceived as the art of getting things done through people. In a broader sense, it is the process of planning, organizing, leading and controlling the efforts of members of an organization /institution and using all the organizational goals and objectives. The interrelated activities and functions of administration include: planning, organizing, leadership, control and development. These actions are normally carried out by individuals (managers, administrators, organization or institutional stakeholders, government officials, etc.).

The strategies include proper and effective leadership, discipline, supervision, planning, delegation of duties, monitoring of staff and students activities, motivation of staff, establishment of channels of communication between themselves and their staff and identification of problems. School authorities should also see that students receive adequate teaching and learning through the efforts of both academic and non-academic staff. Thus, administrative strategies of secondary schools are mechanism for ensuring an appropriate learning process. It is the degree of control over what is permitted as an education experience, ensuring that the institution complies with basic requirements, or is accountable to its stakeholders, including funders and students or has processes in place to enhance the learning process (Walson & Ajekere, 2020).

Principals' Motivational Strategy and Teachers Job Performance

Many opinions have been adduced to explain the meaning of motivation while the concept of motivation is derived from the term “motive” which is an inner state that activate people to

exhibit positive or negative behaviour towards personal or group goals. Motivation is an inner state that energises or moves and directs or channels behaviour towards goal achievement. It has to do with drives, needs wishes and forces which have to be satisfied. Kalu (2006) described motivation as the mechanism which controls behaviour. That is to say that motivation is the force that maintains and alters the direction, quality and intensity of behaviour. Teachers are indispensable for developing the prospect of the educational system. Achieving level of schools is directly related with the productivity of the teachers. Motivation develops the productivity of the teachers for effective functioning in the education sector. Productivity is enhanced from 25% to 85.90%, when teachers are motivated either by intrinsic or extrinsic model

Intrinsic motivation is determined by an interest or enjoyment in the work itself, and it is developed within the person rather than relying on someone else. Intrinsic motivation includes personal accomplishment, relationship between bosses and subordinate, relationship with colleagues, recognition for work done, achievement, increased responsibility, growth through self-development etc. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is the reward in form of pay raise, supervision of subordinates, regular promotion, a cash bonus, interpersonal relationship, fame, a gift, good working condition etc. In other words, motivation inspired the teachers to put efforts to achieve academic excellence. Robert-Okah (2014) postulated that motivation is an important aspect of personal management as it determines to a large extent the productivity of teachers. It is a general belief that a happy employee is a dedicated employee and that which is good for the organization is also good for the workers. Contrary, lack of motivation is manifested in teachers' lack of interest in performing their tasks thereby hindered dedication and goal achievement.

Principals' motivation plays a very important role in the promotion of teaching and learning excellences. This is because principals are a great number of human resources elements and have a great impact on quality of education in schools (Muller et al., 2011). This goes to say that a motivated principal will likely motivate the teachers serving under him, and generally, motivated teachers are more likely to motivate students to learn in the classroom to ensure the implementation of educational goals and feelings of satisfaction and fulfillment. While principals' motivation is fundamental to the teaching and learning process, several principals are not highly motivated. This observation needs to be taken seriously.

Motivational Techniques of Principal for Teachers Motivation and Job Satisfaction

Motivational techniques are considered as methods that encourages an individual's goal related behaviour. They are motivational stimuli consciously used to achieve some systematic and lasting positive effect and optimal task performance from teachers in secondary educational system. These strategies among others include:

Good Work Environment: Teachers work environment is the school. It constitutes important factor in teachers' motivation and job satisfaction. In Nigeria, the teachers' working environment has been described as the most improved of all sector of labor force. Public secondary schools in Rivers State are not exception as the condition of most of these schools especially in the rural parts of the state is quite pitiable. Facilities in most of these schools are dilapidated and inadequate and the principals in these schools appear to neither be reluctant over it nor make frantic efforts within their scope of employment as school managements to remedy the situation. Chandrasekar (2011) posited that school environment can affect productivity, motivation and wellbeing of teachers. The working environment of teachers also determines the attitude and

behaviour of teachers towards their work. Several studies show that the environment is related to teacher job satisfaction and improvement on it has positive effect on both teachers and learners. Thus, it is important for administrators to create enabling working environment.

Recognition: Recognition involves using rewards to encourage good behaviour in teachers. Teachers' recognition is one of the vital keys to motivation available for use by principals. It promotes trust as a factor in job satisfaction of a teacher within his principal. It is a motivational strategy, which involves the use of intangible incentives that shows gratitude and offering of praise. Teachers are motivated when reward is related to performance on contribution and also perceived as fair and equitable. The principals need to recognize and encourage teachers that perform outstandingly. Teachers can be given cash rewards, praise and other gifts to motivate them towards high performance.

Provision of Incentives: Part of the reward system capable of boosting teachers' morale is incentives. According to Arikes and Garske (2001), incentives are referred to as objects, events or condition that incites a person to action. They are expressions of a person's need which are external to him. Incentives are those things a person perceives in his environment as being helpful to the achievement of his goals. Thus, to satisfy a person, incentives must be present in his environment that will serve as a satisfier. For example, bonus, praise, prize, granting promotion, formal and informal acknowledgements, awarding etc.

Advancement: Teachers' advancement is central to motivation because it positions them to show high performance in their jobs. A teacher would consider advancement as personal growth which involves change in an individual's status or position in an organization. Principals are to ensure that teachers get resources to add and change their roles and take more responsibilities. Most teachers would prefer to learn new things in their jobs and would put in more efforts if inspired by their principals with roles which its accomplishment will lead to advancement. The principal also through this promotes the capabilities of the teacher. A teacher can be encouraged by a principal to further his education as a step for bringing advancement, permitting the teacher to enroll for masters and doctoral programmes will pave a way for him to be eligible to be considered for elevation to higher positions.

School Management Support: School management support through encouragement and attention to the personal and on the job needs of workers, constitute important factor in employee motivation. In Nigeria, teachers are facing many personal and on the job problems, which are undermining their effectiveness in schools. There are those that are financially bankrupt to the extent of not being able to afford the basic needs such as food, clothes, shelter and money. There are also some who might be having unsettled home due to conflict and this makes them to be emotionally distracted from work. Some are suffering from ailments which might be undermining their effectiveness and regularity in schools and classes. Principals can assist teachers who have financial needs to access loans from the banks or give loans to such teachers if their financial base meets such financial demand is adequate. In case of those teachers having marital conflicts, the Head of the school can mediate in such conflict if need be. Those having low qualifications among the teachers can be encouraged and assisted in getting approval for in-service education from the appropriate quarters. Koumen and Thijs (2011) observed that

managerial support largely contributes to teachers' overall well-being. Hence, there is a need for principals to give priority to it.

Principals' Supervision Strategies and Teachers' Job Performance

Supervision is perceived as those activities which are conducted by the supervisor (both internal and external) with the main aim of sensitizing, mobilizing, and motivating or stimulating the teachers in the school towards improved instructional task performance to optimally achieve stated objectives and goals that transcend the system. It is aimed at improving not only the quality and standard of teachers but also, the level of performance of the students (Oragwu & Nwabueze 2015). The dire need for adequate and effective instructional supervision in secondary schools is very important considering the high rate at which non-professionals such as holders of National Diploma (ND), Higher National Diploma (HND) and first-degree holders in other disciplines are being employed as teachers. These non-professional teachers are even posted to teach subjects not related to their area of specialization.

Many of these non-professionals in the system are not even willing to go for a post-graduate diploma in education (PDGE), coupled with the fact that many of our colleges of education and universities turn out half-baked teachers into the educational industry (Madumere-Obike, 2004). Many of these teachers even after graduation lack self-confidence and teaching competence, because they do not have in-depth knowledge of the subjects they are expected to teach. They also lack adequate knowledge of the principles and techniques of teaching and classroom management. If an effective method of instructional supervision is not employed by the principals to assist these teachers, it will have adverse effects on the process of teaching and learning in our schools. The principal as a supervisor assesses and records the performance of teachers, their ability and consistency in carrying out the classroom activities. The activities of the principal as the supervisor include: Inspection, monitoring, rating, assisting, recommending etc. All these activities if carried out professionally, will aim at improving teachers' productivity in instructional delivery.

Principals' supervision in the modern era centres on the improvement of the teaching-learning situation to the benefit of both the teachers and learners. This is because it helps in the identification of areas of strengths and weaknesses of teachers. This implies a follow-up activity that is equally directed at the improvement of identified areas of teachers' weaknesses thus creating a cordial working atmosphere based on good human relations. Thus, the principal as a catalyst facilitates the implementation of the various sets of instructional activities geared towards an effective, viable, vibrant and qualitative educational system that will improve the teaching-learning situation.

The targets of supervision as revealed by Nwakpa (2014), aim to ensure that minimum standards are met, providing equal educational opportunities for all children by maintaining set school standards. It also offers a platform for constructive advice to improve teaching quality and educational facilities. Additionally, supervision ensures prudent use of public funds in running schools and provides accurate reports on human and material resources to relevant authorities. It encourages desirable education practices, discourages negative ones, and lays a foundation for local and large-scale initiatives by teachers, principals, inspectors, and the government (Nwakpa, 2014). In the view of Okibe (2008), the teachers also play an internal supervisory role that helps the school head to achieve the goals and objectives of the school. In another development, the principals supervise the cooperation that exists between the school and the Parent Teachers

Association (PTA) in maintaining healthy relationships with parents and guardians. Thus, the Parents' Teachers Association provides the principals with an easy avenue for achieving supervisory objectives. It is the duty of the principal as an internal supervisor to meet problems that are connected with students' welfare, progress and shortcoming.

According to Nwagwu in Ogbonnaya (2005), principals as internal supervisors play a crucial role in the school system by organizing the school timetable and overseeing day-to-day operations, managing and maintaining school facilities, coordinating teacher activities, supervising extracurricular activities, and maintaining high standards of conduct and discipline. They also control and supervise the business aspects of school life, manage finances, and maintain various records. Additionally, principals foster good school-community relationships, participate in community development projects, and support teacher professional growth by encouraging participation in training programs and workshops. By performing these tasks, principals ensure the smooth operation of the school and promote a conducive learning environment.

Supervision is one of the strategies a well-determined and focused administrator uses to influence the activity of his subjects and to bring about efficiency and effectiveness in the school system. Efficient and effective teachers are the product of intense and conscious supervision which is targeted at enhancing human resource utilization. The principal as a leader of the group of teachers in the school system has the function of interacting with the teachers in order to improve the learning situation for the students through instructional supervision. Instructional supervision is one of the processes by which school administrators attempt to achieve acceptable standards of performance and results. It is the tool of quality control in the school system and a phase of school administration which focuses primarily on the achievement of expectations of the educational system. (Peretomode, 2006).

Principal's Supervisory Techniques

The school principal as the instructional leader is entrusted with the responsibility of improving the quality of instructional delivery through adequate supervision of teachers. To support this, Ugboka (2012) stated that the school principals are the management whose responsibility is to provide a variety of supervisory techniques for teachers to see the need for change and change plans. There are several instructional supervisory techniques. Iloh et al. (2016) listed a variety of supervision techniques including classroom visitation/observation, inter/intra school, team teaching practices, workshops, observation, clinical supervision and micro-teaching among others. This is also in line with Ani (2007) who outlined supervision techniques as follows: classroom visitation, micro-teaching, research approach, workshop, demonstration techniques and tape recording. The supervisory techniques outlined by the above scholars adopted in this study are classroom visitation/observation, workshop, micro-teaching, inter/intra school and demonstration.

School principals employ various supervisory techniques to enhance teachers' job performance and improve instructional delivery. These techniques include classroom visitation/observation, workshops, micro-teaching, inter/intra-school, and demonstration (Iloh et al., 2016; Ani, 2007). Classroom visitation/observation allows principals to assess teachers' mastery of subject matter, teaching strategies, and classroom management. Workshops provide a platform for exchanging ideas and sharing experiences to acquire new knowledge and skills. Micro-teaching involves training teachers in specific skills, receiving feedback, and re-teaching

lessons for improvement. The demonstration technique enables principals to model effective teaching methods, stimulating teacher growth and discovering new ideas (Eze cited in Sule, 2013). These supervisory techniques aim to support teachers in identifying areas for improvement, developing their skills, and delivering high-quality instruction, ultimately enhancing their job performance.

Principals' Communication Strategies and Teacher Job Performance

Over the years, effective information dissemination and communication in education has been a source of creating awareness on issues in educational institutions. Communication is one of most essential processes in every institution. It is very important factor in any institution to attain success. Communication is the link that creates a relationship between people. In marriage institution, it is the key to intimacy (Wright, 2000). In business organization, it is the lifeblood of a successful organization, it serves as the foundation for all organizations as organizations cannot perform the basic functions of management such as planning, organizing, leading, and controlling (Gupta, 2016). In academic institutions, communication is the link between knowledgeable principal, teacher and learning students. Hence, teaching and learning cannot occur without communication.

According to Stephen (2011), communication is a critical factor in directing and mobilising the workforce towards the accomplishment of organizational goals and objectives. It is the vehicle through which the basic management and administrative functions are carried out. Managers and administrators direct through communication, and they coordinate through communication, and the staff, plans and control through communication. It is a give-and-take method involving the sender and the receiver (Nakpodia 2006). The importance of effective communication between principals and staff in a school system cannot be overemphasized. This is because every administrative function and activity in a school involves some form of direct or indirect communication. Whether planning and organizing or leading and monitoring, school administrators communicate with and through other people.

This implies that principal's communication skills and styles affect both personnel and schools' effectiveness (Brun, 2010). It seems reasonable therefore to say that one of the inhibiting forces to effective teachers' job performance and school effectiveness is the lack of effective communication between the leaders and the subordinate. For the school principal to make sound and coherent decisions, plan, organize, control etc., he must map out strategies for receiving and passing information to every individual within the school especially the teachers, for effective management. Principals' communication patterns can fast-track the achievement of school goals if well handled by the principal, or hamper school effectiveness if it is poorly managed.

Communication Patterns

Communication patterns refer to the communication network in school as an organization. It outlines the different directions through which information flows within the organization. The patterns of contact among the members of the organization and the flow of information among them are communication networks. Individuals within the organization deploy various techniques or ways to share useful work-related information. The pattern could be formal or informal, the formal or official pattern usually follows the organizational hierarchical structure to

convey work-related information. In some instances and for some purposes, the school principal can adopt the informal method to reach out to the workers, in such cases, the official or formal protocol is bypassed.

There are many types of communication patterns in schools as organizations and the principals will require a certain structure for their communication. An effective school principal does not rely on one pattern of communication to relate with different people, he adopts different patterns based on the prevailing situation and what he wants to achieve at the moment and also the dynamic of the people involved or he wants to communicate with. As important as principals' communication is to the school system, one observes that many schools' principals' communication pattern is nothing to write home about because of the type adopted by some of them which fails to integrate the stakeholders (teachers, students, parents and community). In the activities of the school, principals' communication pattern can therefore be described as the way and manner principals pass information to their subordinates and this is quite germane to the effective functioning of the school system.

Effective communication is vital in enhancing teachers' job performance. School principals employ various communication patterns to achieve this goal. Upward communication allows teachers to share reports, suggestions, and concerns with the principal, fostering a sense of ownership and involvement. Downward communication enables principals to convey directives, objectives, and policies to teachers, ensuring everyone is on the same page. Horizontal communication between peers, such as Heads of Departments, promotes the exchange of ideas and coordination of educational activities. Face-to-face communication offers a personal touch, allowing principals to motivate teachers and provide immediate feedback. Principals can empower teachers, promote collaboration, and ultimately enhance job performance, leading to improved student outcomes and school effectiveness.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a correlational research design to investigate the relationship between principals' administrative strategies and teachers' job performance. The population comprised 2,005 academic staff from 37 senior public secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria. A random sample of 700 teachers, representing 53% of the population, was selected using a random sampling technique. A questionnaire titled "Principals' Administrative Strategies and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire" (PASTJ PQ) was developed and validated by experts in the field. The instrument consisted of two sections: Section A (demographic data) and Section B (questionnaire items based on the study's variables). The items were rated on a modified Likert scale, with a criterion mean of 2.50. The instrument's reliability was established using the Cronbach Alpha that yielded a reliability index value of .760. The questionnaire was administered to the respondents by the researcher and two trained research assistants, with a retrieval rate of 97% (680). Data analysis was conducted using mean, standard deviation, and Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) with SPSS version 22. The analysis aimed to answer research questions and test hypotheses at a .05 significance level.

RESULT

Answer to Research Questions

Research Question 1: How does a principal's motivational strategy enhance teachers' job performance in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean ratings and Standard deviation on how principal's motivational strategy enhances teachers' job performance in Rivers State?

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1	Teachers' efforts in instructional activities are recognized by the principal	3.15	0.75	Agree
2	The principal ensures that teachers are promoted regularly.	2.91	1.01	Agree
3	Principal motivate teachers with cash rewards, prizes and other gifts.	3.08	0.78	Agree
4	Principal praises exceptional teachers during staff meetings.	3.04	0.88	Agree
5	Principal provides adequate teaching aids for each subject.	1.95	0.93	Disagree
6	Principal assist teachers who have financial needs to access loan from the bank.	2.98	0.94	Agree
Grand Mean		2.85	0.88	Agree

Table 1 shows the Mean ratings and Standard deviation on how principal's motivational strategy enhance teachers' job performance in Rivers State. The table reveals that the majority of the respondents agreed that the ways principal's motivational strategy enhance teachers' job performance in Rivers State includes teachers' efforts in instructional activities are recognized by the principal, principal ensures that teaches are promoted on regular basis, principal motivate teachers with cash rewards, prizes and other gifts, principal praises exceptional teachers during staff meetings, principal assist teachers who have financial needs to access loan from the bank as seen on item on item 1, 2, 3, 4 and 6 with the mean ratings of 3.15, 2.91, 3.08, 3.04 and 2.98. In this same vein, from the ranking order item 7 came 1st with the mean value of 3.15 and item 11 came last. From the foregoing, the grand mean value of 2.85 shows that the answer to research 1 is that principal's motivational strategy enhance teachers' job performance in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: How does principal's effective supervision strategy improve teachers' job performance in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean ratings and standard deviation on how principal's effective supervision strategy improve teachers' job performance in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
7	Good supervision practices by the principal help to furnish teachers with information/suggestions for effective instructional task performance.	2.90	0.95	Agree
8	Provide an opportunity to evaluate teachers' performance in the classroom.	3.11	0.95	Agree
9	Supervisors hold interactive sessions with teachers after classroom observation to find solutions to identified problems.	3.05	0.87	Agree
10	Principal's supervisory practices provide teachers with the knowledge of improved teaching methods.	2.97	0.95	Agree
11	Supervision exposes teachers to better ways of writing their lesson notes/plans.	2.12	1	Disagree
12	Conferences organized by principals allow the accumulation of valuable resources for the professional development of teachers	2.98	0.95	Agree
Grand Mean		2.86	0.95	Agree

Data in Table 2 shows the mean ratings and standard deviation on the how principal's effective supervision strategy improves teachers' job performance in Rivers State. The table shows how principal's effective supervision strategy improves teachers' job performance in Rivers State; good supervision practices by the principal help to furnish teachers with information/suggestions for effective instructional task performance, provide an opportunity to evaluate teachers' performance in the classroom, supervisors hold interactive sessions with teachers after classroom observation to find solutions to identified problems, principal's supervisory practices provide teachers with the knowledge of improved teaching methods, conferences organized by principals allow the accumulation of valuable resources for the professional development of teachers as seen on item 7, 8, 9, 10 and 12 with the weighted mean scores of 2.9, 3.11, 3.05, 2.97, and 2.98 respectively. However, the respondents disagreed that supervision exposes teachers to better ways of writing their lesson notes/plan. as seen in item 11 with the weighted mean value of 2.12. From the ranking order, item 8 came 1st and item 11 came last, further, the overall grand mean of 2.86 shows that principals' communication improves teachers' job performance in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: How do principal's communication strategies enhance teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean ratings and standard deviation on how principal's communication strategies enhance teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
13	The principal keeps teachers informed about important school matters.	2.7	1.05	Agree
14	There is an open-door policy that encourages teachers to walk in and talk to principals on issues related to school.	2.94	1.03	Agree
15	The principal uses multiple channels of communication in the school.	2.89	1.02	Agree
16	There is effective communication between the principal and teachers.	2.96	0.96	Agree
17	The principal directs teachers through communication.	2.06	1.02	Disagree
18	Communication is the vehicle through which the basic management and administrative functions are carried out.	3.04	1.04	Agree
Grand mean		2.77	1.02	Agree

Data on Table 3 show the mean ratings and standard deviation on how principal's communication strategies enhances teachers' job performance. The Table shows that the ways principal's communication strategies enhances teachers' job performance includes; principal keeps teachers informed about important school matters, there is a open door policy that encourages teachers to walk in and talk to principals on issues related to school, principal uses multiple channels of communication in the school, there is effective communication between principal and teachers, communication is the vehicle through which the basic management and administrative function are carried out as seen on items 13, 14, 15, 16, and 18 with the mean scores of 2.7, 2.94, 2.89, 2.96, 3.04 respectively which were all above the criterion mean scores of 2.50. However, the majority of the respondents disagreed that the principal directs teachers through communication. As seen in item 5 with a mean rating of 2.06. From the ranking order, item 18 came highest with a mean score of 3.04, while item 17 came lowest with a mean score of 2.06. Again, the overall grand mean score of 2.77 shows that principals' communication strategies enhance teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

All the hypotheses in the study were tested using the calculated Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). At various significant levels, the r-values were first converted to t-values to enable the researcher to establish the required relationship.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between principals' motivational strategy and teacher's job performance in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of correlation analysis on the significant relationship between principals' motivational strategy and teacher's job performance in Rivers State

Variables	N	r-crit.	Df	t-cal.	t-crit.	Decision
Motivation Strategy	680	0.43	678	7.969	±1.96	Rejected
Teachers Job Performance						

Data in Table 4 indicated that at 678 degrees of freedom and at 0.05 level of significance, the r-critical value 0.43 and 2-tailed significant value stood at 0.00. The t-calculated value of 7.969 was by far greater than t-critical value of ± 1.96 . Based on this observation, the researcher fails to accept the null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis. Hence, a moderate positive relationship exists between principals' motivational strategy and teacher's job performance in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between principals' effective supervision strategy and teacher's job performance in Rivers State.

Table 5: Summary of correlation analysis on the significant relationship between principals' effective supervision strategy and teacher's job performance in Rivers State

Variables	n	r-crit.	Df	t-cal	t-crit.	Decision
Supervision Strategy	680	0.35	678	6.25	±1.96	Rejected
Teachers Job Performance						

Data in Table 5 indicated that at 678 degrees of freedom and at .05 level of significance, the r-critical value was 0.35 and the 2-tailed significant value stood at 0.000. The t-calculated value of 6.25 was by far greater than the t-critical value of ± 1.96 . Based on this observation, the researcher fails to accept the null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis. Hence, a significant relationship exists between principals' effective supervision strategy and teacher's job performance in Rivers State.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between principals' communication pattern strategy and teacher's job performance in Rivers State.

Table 6: Summary of correlation analysis on the relationship between principals' effective supervision strategy and teacher's job performance in Rivers State

Variables	n	r-crit.	Df	t-cal	t-crit.	Decision
Effective Supervision Strategy	680	0.45	678	8.43	±1.96	Rejected
Job performance						

Data in Table 6 indicated that at 678 degree of freedom and at .05 level of significance, the r-critical value 0.45 and 2-tailed significant value stood at 0.00. The t-calculated value of 8.43 was by far greater than t-critical value of ± 1.96 . Based on this observation, the researcher fails to accept the null hypothesis and accepts the alternative hypothesis. Hence, significant relationship exists between principals' communication pattern strategy and teacher's job performance in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

How Principal' Motivational Strategy Enhances Teachers Job Performance in Senior Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State

The findings of the study reveals that the ways principal's motivational strategy enhance teachers' job performance in Rivers State includes; teachers' efforts in instructional activities are recognized by the principal, principal ensures that teaches are promoted on regular basis, principal motivate teachers with cash rewards, prizes and other gifts, principal praises exceptional teachers during staff meetings, principal assist teachers who have financial needs to access loan from the bank. The findings of the study is in line with Kalu (2006) who described motivation as the mechanism which controls behavior. That is to say that motivation is the force that maintains and alters the direction, quality and intensity of behaviour. Principals' motivation plays a very important role in the promotion of teaching and learning excellences. This is because principals are chief administrators in secondary schools that makes sure that the aims and objectives of the school system; hence, they are elements that have a great impact on quality of education in schools. Also, Robert-Okah (2014) is of the view that motivation is an important aspect of personal management as it determines to a large extent the productivity of teachers. When teachers are happy with the principals when they are motivated with praises, they tend put in their best for an effective service in secondary schools in Rivers State. Contrary, lack of motivation is manifested in teachers' lack of interest in performing their tasks thereby hinder goal achievement.

How principal's Effective Supervision Strategy Improve Teachers' Job Performance in Rivers State

The findings of the study showed how principal's effective supervision strategy improve teachers' job performance in Rivers State includes; good supervision practices by the principal help to furnish teachers with information/suggestions for effective instructional task performance, provide an opportunity to evaluate teachers' performance in the classroom, supervisors hold interactive sessions with teachers after classroom observation to find solutions to identified problems, principal's supervisory practices provide teachers with the knowledge of

improved teaching methods, conferences organized by principals allow the accumulation of valuable resources for the professional development of teachers. These findings are in accordance with Oragwu and Nwabueze (2015) having opined that supervision is aimed at improving not only the quality and standard of teachers but also, the level of performance of the students. Supervision involves providing expert assistance to teachers to help them acquire more skills and competencies for effective teaching. It therefore means that effective supervision is an essential quality service rendered to teachers, focusing on how to help them understand and accept themselves, their abilities patterns of interest, emotional make-up and background preparation and helping them set realistic goals for themselves.

In school administration, the administrators are burdened with this responsibility of providing expert assistance to the teachers in all areas of their need for effective teaching and learning. In this same vein, Okibe (2008), opined that the teachers also play an internal supervisory role that helps the school head to achieve the goals and objectives of the school. Also, the finding gained the support of Normakoh (2019), having opined that supervision intends to guide and direct the instructional activities of teachers in line with the professional conduct aimed at ensuring efficiency. The heartbeat of supervision is to monitor the performance of school staff and students, taking note of their strengths, weakness all geared towards improving the standard of performance and also the teaching and learning environment for goal attainment. The concept of supervision is therefore directed to the changing of the behaviour of teachers for effective performance. Supervision is a process of stimulating growth and the means of helping teachers to help them.

How principal's Communication Pattern Strategy on Teachers Job Performance in Senior Public Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

The findings of the study showed that ways principals' communication strategies enhance teachers' job performance includes; principal keeps teachers informed about important school matters, there is an open door policy that encourages teachers to walk in and talk to principals on issues related to school, principal uses multiple channels of communication in the school, there is effective communication between principal and teachers, communication is the vehicle through which the basic management and administrative function are carried. This finding is in line with Stephen (2011), who opined that communication is a critical factor in directing and mobilizing the workforce towards the accomplishment of organizational goals and objectives. He went further to state that it is the vehicle through which the basic management and administrative functions are carried out. Communication is employed in an organization as a strategy to resolve conflict, which is actualized or achieved by breaking down barriers or resistance among workers and promoting their trust. Communication is a rational process which involves initiating messages using symbols and signs to express meaning, create similar understanding and influence actions.

Also, managers and administrators direct through communication, and they coordinate through communication, and the staff, plans and control through communication. It is a give-and-take method involving the sender and the receiver (Nakpodia 2006). It is a process or means by which information is shared among individuals through a common system of symbols, signs or behaviour (Onyeike, 2013). Effective communication is one of the strategies principals or administrators engage in to achieve the stated goals of education and resolve crises that may arise to destabilize the performance of the staff and the general peace of the school system.

CONCLUSION

This study has established the different principal's strategies to enhance the performance of teachers in secondary schools. The study also made it clear how communication pattern and effective supervision strategy enhances teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings of the study indicated that the application of supervision as a management strategy stimulates and quickens the staff for improved performance in the school system. It therefore meant that through supervision teachers tend to be more focused in their service delivery by putting in their best for the achievement of the goals of education. Also, active communication promotes mutual interaction and cooperation among staff for optimum productivity. The study revealed that communication resolves disputes that may arise in the course of the administration and helps in pursuing the goals and objectives of the school system.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study and conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

- Principals should regularly supervise teachers to ensure they deliver their services competently, enhancing teachers' job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.
- Effective communication strategies should be employed by principals to settle issues, unite staff, and achieve educational goals, ultimately enhancing teachers' job performance.
- Principals should implement motivational strategies effectively to encourage teachers to perform at their best, leading to improved job performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

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